

THE IMPORTANCE OF PIANO WORKS IN DEVELOPING COMPETENCES OF INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE IN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11280449>

Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical foundations of the development of musical instrument performance competences in music education students of the higher pedagogical education system and the importance of piano pieces.

Key words: Musical education, musical instrument performance, commentary, textbook, choir, methodological preparation, piano.

Introduction.

In recent years, there have been political and economic changes in all spheres of new Uzbekistan, as well as great changes in the field of public education. The implementation of the Law "On Education" and the National Program "Training of Personnel" entered the stage of quality indicators.

The state educational standard, the curriculum, the creation of New Generation textbooks, and the promotion of cultural development to higher levels, serve to realize the noble goals aimed at taking a worthy place among the world community. Mastering new educational standards, encouraging independent thinking, working on the basis of new technology directly depends on the activity of the teacher. Modern technology is becoming one of the decisive factors in increasing the efficiency of education, ensuring the fulfillment of state educational standards, and guaranteeing the quality indicator of education. Each profession requires having its own important qualities. Determining such conditions is the determination of specific goals for the formation of the personality of young students.¹ The goal of the modern pedagogic education system is to achieve continuous general and professional improvement of the teacher who belongs to the new category, because the general education school sets high demands on the teacher, his professional qualifications and personal qualities.

Teacher training is carried out by means of the entire educational and educational work in the higher educational institution, the educational process and extracurricular work are considered its main components. A regular approach ensures that students use all the opportunities of higher education to develop the knowledge, skills, and personal qualities necessary for the teaching profession. Among the tools to successfully solve this task, the composition of the foundations of pedagogical skills for the field of music-pedagogy is of great importance. This tool is a component of the system of professional training of future teachers. The theoretical knowledge and preparation of students creates favorable conditions for expanding their scope of knowledge, serves as a means of forming the personality of a future music teacher, helps students to develop pedagogical skills and abilities, the mood of a creative approach to this music, to develop their own spiritual help to develop skills such as

¹ Muhammadjonova Z "Methodology of teaching piano playing" Tashkent.: 2006, 6 p.

being able to control the situation, understanding and understanding the emotional state of another person.

Note in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "*On Education*".

"*Education is universal and national cultural The priority of values is the policy of our country in education determines the main direction*"². Fundamentally reforming the education system in our country, raising it to the level of modern requirements, creating an updated system of national personnel training is one of the most important issues. In particular, improving the professional skills of future music teachers, shaping and developing pedagogical qualities in them is one of the highest goals facing the direction of music education in higher education. A separate chapter of the concept of music education in secondary schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan is devoted to the set of modern music teachers and their professional qualities. It is stated in the document: "*Today's music teacher is highly cultured, has boundless devotion to his profession, and advanced pedagogical thinking must be the owner*". He must have the capacity for continuous professional and cultural development. He needs to have deep knowledge and skills in music, aesthetics, pedagogy and psychology-physiology, in particular, music teaching methodology. Especially in the profession of a music teacher, it is necessary to embody the qualities of playing an instrument, singing, conducting a choir, and theorizing music.

Today's music teacher is a scientific thinker, a master of advanced experiences, inquisitive and creative, and should strive to discover new forms and methods of music education. It is necessary to connect and enrich the content of music education with the content of other subjects and everyday life. The advanced experience and new methods discovered by the inquisitive and creative teacher are the main support and source of inspiration for the continuous improvement and development of music education in the school. A knowledgeable and experienced music teacher, as an art intellectual, is the leader of musical and educational work in the school. In order to form the modern requirements for the teacher's professional qualities, it is necessary to take measures during the student period. After all, the professionogram of the pedagogical skills of a music teacher requires the creation of a system of requirements for a music teacher in the field of specialization.

I. Methodological preparation:

1. To understand the essence of social development and the laws of musical art.
2. The ability to conduct public propaganda and musical educational work in various forms.
3. Knowing the moral education (methodology) and being able to apply it in the practice of aesthetic education.

II. Psychological-Pedagogical preparation.

1. To know the basics of psychological-pedagogical science, the theory of education, the psychology of musical art, and the laws of psychological development of a person.
2. To know the theoretical material from pedagogy-psychology in depth, to know in depth the methodology of educational work, to be able to apply its main aspects in educational practice.
3. To know the psychology of musical abilities, to form musical needs and interests of students of different ages to know the pedagogical and psychological laws.

² Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 23.09.2020 No. ORQ-637, <https://lex.uz/docs/-5013007>

4. The ability to critically evaluate one's professional activity, continuous improvement of personal pedagogical skills.

5. To acquire the qualification of conducting psychological and pedagogical experiments, to be able to draw scientific results and conclusions confirming the research hypothesis.

III. General methodological and special methodological training.

1. In-depth knowledge of the theoretical foundations of mass musical education and teaching methodology.

2. Reasonably planning the educational process and enriching it with corrections, being able to choose music-didactic material in an appropriate way, and be able to deliver it.

3. Use of didactic principles and methods in the lesson of music culture, formation of basic musical knowledge, formation of interests of students in the educational process of different age stages.

4. Ability to manage and control the work of the educational team.

5. Ability to work with scientific-methodical literature in a reasonable and methodical way, preparation of methodical recommendations on the problem of musical aesthetic education.

IV. Musical pedagogical preparation.

- Musical-theoretical knowledge of music theory and history;

- To deeply understand the essence of the interdependence and universal characteristics of the music art of Uzbekistan and the world music culture, to understand their interrelationship with socio-historical conditions;

- To be able to analyze musical works, to understand them completely, to understand them logically;

- To acquire knowledge, qualifications and skills in choir conducting and vocal performance;

- Ability to read choral scores, performance and choral vocal analysis of works;

- Full mastery of the qualifications and skills of conducting techniques;

- To learn how to add voice, engage in voice education;

- Having knowledge and skills in musical performance and accompaniment activities, the ability to play musical instruments;

- Obtaining the qualification of musical performance and solo performance;

- Thorough knowledge of the features of accompanying children's singing and musical instruments;

- Being able to read the notation of solo and ensemble works.

V. The qualification of conducting various works in the musical-educational direction:

extracurricular and extracurricular work on aesthetic education activity as an organizer;

promoter of the art of music;

public speaking, music performance, accompaniment;

musical and sociological research, etc.

Thus, pedagogical skill is a matter of great importance as the basis of the professional activity of a music teacher. Therefore, among the systematic requirements for a music teacher, there is a requirement to have knowledge and skills in playing an instrument, to be able to

play a certain instrument skillfully. We chose the piano in this regard, motivated by its sound capabilities and the fact that every secondary school is equipped with this instrument.

It is aimed at teaching the piano in educational institutions classes are organized based on the general didactic principles of musical education, on the basis of specially developed programs, and on the basis of methodical resources for learning the piano instrument, so that this process should be considered as a unique integrated system.

The behavior of the future music teacher at all stages, starting from the initial period of piano training, based on the current goals of musical-aesthetic education and specific educational and educational tasks of the course, determines the content of education. The main goals and objectives of education and upbringing of students in the piano class of general music education originate from the nature of the demands placed on the education of the young generation by our government.

It is known from the theory of pedagogy that a person is fully mature finding in the unity of labor, mental, aesthetic and physical types of education provided in the activity. Music education and upbringing, due to its nature of aesthetic education, aims to direct the interest, love and enthusiasm of young people involved in the field of art to the right path. the most important factor for the successful perspective of this process is the correct formation of creative and performing abilities, the development of feeling and understanding of beauty in art and life, engaging in music, learning the secrets of its performance in one's life plans to convert it to needs. Unless such a goal is set, and learning a musical instrument becomes "just a hobby", such education will have no meaning.

The content, nature and implementation of aesthetic education, requirements from the point of view of learning musical instruments, first of all, requires working in accordance with musical-educational and musical-educational goals and tasks aimed at their implementation. These are the best examples created based on the works of world nations, great composers, modern and folk music works of Uzbek composers and composers to form students' general musical, musical theoretical knowledge, and practical performance skills. to familiarize them with, through this, to develop their aesthetic taste, worldview, and to turn children into active participants of artistic hobby.

Independent, artistic amateur piano clubs and can study in non-school educational institutions. Education is not only about teaching children how to play an instrument, but also about instilling interest and love in the art of music in students, helping them to grow in general music, developing musical-creative and performing abilities, and deepening their understanding of musical works. and it is intended to achieve that they can evaluate independently. As students improve their performance skills, teaching them to work independently is also an important task.

Practicing pedagogues think about the development of musical performance, performance abilities and skills of students, and in their concluding remarks, they are sufficient for children to learn to play musical instruments at an amateur level, to learn any piece independently, gradually according to the notes. it is emphasized that they analyze musical literacy, reality depicted in music, and emotional experiences at the level of students of special schools.³ In this activity, children regularly listen to more music and do their initial theoretical analysis, acquire the skills of reading from a sheet (according to the note), learn

³ Muhamadjonova Z. "Methodology of piano ensemble teaching" Tashkent.: 2006, 8 p.

some parts of some, not so complicated, samples of folk music as much as possible, and then weave It is necessary for them to be able to play by heart (by recalling what they heard).

In the system of general music education, the theoretical and practical knowledge of teaching students to play a musical instrument, in particular, the piano, and in the process of forming their musical performance abilities, skills and qualifications, is on the one hand, musical instrument performance. with effective scientific research aimed at some problems of musical-aesthetic education of amateurs, and on the other hand, the development of a scientifically-based integrated system of providing excellent musical-aesthetic education to students, such a system as the theory, practice, methods and tools of teaching students to play the piano (categories of important forms) are characterized by unmarkedness.

He is taking lessons to learn the piano the lack of teaching and methodical resources that illuminate the integrated methodical system and its organizational and methodical foundations that allow students to successfully master the performance of this instrument, insufficient provision of educational institutions with them and many pedagogues working there - that the methodical training of teachers and musicians is not up to the required level, the aesthetic attitude of the students to the art of music is sufficient the reason is that it is not formed at the level, the musical-performance activity has not acquired a social character. In musical instrument training, performance skills are formed in a scattered manner, individual performance does not include practical musical skills in ensemble performance, music perception, performance, and musical creativity are focused on. The lack of connections between different types of activities is a serious obstacle to providing excellent musical education to students.

Students in the organization of educational activities in the piano class The need to take age and capabilities into account has been mentioned in many literatures.

Also, the more important components of skills and competencies, that is, the formation of educational, thematic, and mental competencies, are also emphasized. As a result of the study, analysis and personal observations of the scientific, methodological and educational literature on the most important tasks for piano lessons, it is appropriate to act based on the following factors we came to the conclusion that.

Instrument training (teaching system) is based on the system of musicology and piano teaching (Shkola igry na fortepiano);

The skills of perceiving and feeling music in the learning process desire to educate;

Organization of classes as a subject, in its specific way taking into account additional sciences when determining the structure and procedure of their mastery;

Taking into account individual mental feelings of the student and directing them to creative activity.

In this place, there is also a certain educational training on performance skills, independent and creative engagement with music, analysis of musical works, its artistic and aesthetic evaluation, performance and oral interpretation of musical works integrating work into the content of general activities.

Conclusion.

Lessons in the piano class include only certain works, exercises, In this process, it is necessary to engage children in interrelated types of activities aimed at making them interested in music and encouraging them, so that it is not limited to a narrow direction, such

as mastering performance techniques and skills. Studying works of different genres, forms and styles, developing technical skills while playing, practicing and mastering etudes, reading from a sheet, accompanying, playing in accompaniment with a leader, hearing and seeing sounds.

The teacher demands to generalize the activities of piano teaching without separating different types from each other, around the main task of the student. In this place, creativity, initiative, ingenuity, methodical preparation are required from the teacher himself.

The performance repertoire selected for reading and listening to music from a sheet serves to develop the student's musical imagination, thinking, and perception abilities.⁴

⁴ Muhamadjonova Z. "Piano teaching methodology" Tashkent.: 2006, 5 p.

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